

NONLINEAR DIMENSIONALITY REDUCTION OF MIXED-TYPE FEATURE SPACE BASED ON GENERALIZED ASSESSMENTS AND LATENT FEATURE ANALYSIS

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Abstract: Dimensionality reduction is one of the important problems in machine learning and intellectual data analysis, especially when objects are described by mixed-type features measured in different scales. Methodology for dimensionality reduction of heterogeneous feature space is developed using nonlinear transformations, membership functions, generalized assessments and latent features.

The stability and informativeness of features are evaluated, and an agglomerative hierarchical grouping algorithm is applied to form a set of latent features. These latent features are interpreted as generalized assessments of objects and can be used as a new feature space for classification.

Keywords: dimensionality reduction, heterogeneous features, nonlinear transformation, generalized assessment, latent features, classification

Introduction. In modern intelligent systems, a large number of features increases computational complexity and may reduce the learning and generalization capability of models. Therefore, dimensionality reduction and feature selection are widely used to remove redundant, weakly informative, or noisy features [1]. Traditional methods such as PCA and t-SNE are commonly used for dimensionality reduction and visualization, but they may be limited when data contain heterogeneous features measured in different scales [2, 3].

In supervised recognition problems, the transformation of object descriptions from one feature space into another may be performed using both linear and nonlinear models [1, 4, 5]. Linear models are usually simpler and easier to implement, but they may be insufficient when the relationship between features and classes has a complex structure. Nonlinear transformations are more suitable for such cases because they can reveal hidden dependencies between objects and classes and may form a more informative low-dimensional representation of the original data [1, 4, 5]. In this context, latent features are not only reduced representations of the original features but also

generalized assessments that summarize the contribution of several original features to class separation.

This paper proposes a methodology for dimensionality reduction of heterogeneous feature space based on generalized assessments, membership functions, nonlinear transformations, and agglomerative hierarchical grouping [1, 6, 7]. The methodology is theoretically connected with the ideas developed by N.A. Ignatev, and later studies on analytical expressions for latent feature computation. The main goal is to transform quantitative and nominal features into a unified representation, synthesize informative latent features, and improve the generalization ability of classification algorithms in two-class recognition problems.

Theoretical background. The proposed approach is based on the idea that the original feature space may contain redundant, weakly informative, or mixed-type features that make classification difficult [1]. Instead of applying a classifier directly to the original features, the data are first transformed into a new latent feature space, which is consistent with the general idea of nonlinear dimensionality reduction and latent representation construction [1, 4, 5]. Each latent feature is formed from one or several original features and

reflects a generalized assessment of object membership to one of the classes [6, 7].

For nominal features, direct arithmetic operations over gradations are not meaningful. Therefore, nominal gradations are replaced by values of membership functions to classes [1, 6, 7]. This transformation makes it possible to represent nominal values in a numerical form without expanding the dimensionality of the feature space. For quantitative features, class-separating intervals are constructed, and threshold values are determined according to special criteria. As a result, both quantitative and nominal features are brought into a common representation suitable for further grouping and latent feature synthesis.

The formation of latent features can be performed using a hierarchical agglomerative grouping algorithm. In this process, features are gradually combined into nonlinear combinations according to their contribution to class compactness and separation [6]. The resulting latent features may be used in two ways: if a single highly informative latent feature is obtained, it can support rule-based recognition; if several latent features are obtained, they can be used as inputs for precedent-based classifiers such as KNN, SVM, or neural networks [6, 8]. This second case corresponds to a stacking-like interpretation, where the latent feature construction stage acts as a base transformation stage and the final classifier acts as a meta-level recognition algorithm [6, 9].

Problem statement. Let $E_0 = \{S_1, S_2, \dots, S_m\}$ be a training set of objects divided into two mutually disjoint classes K_1 and K_2 .

Each object S_i is described by a feature vector $X^{(n)} = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$, where the feature set contains both quantitative and nominal features. Let X_q denote the set of quantitative features and X_n denote the set of nominal features, were

$$X^{(n)} = X_q \cup X_n, \quad X_q \cap X_n = \emptyset.$$

The main task is to construct a reduced latent feature space

$$Y^{(k)} = (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_k), \quad k < n,$$

where each latent feature y_j is synthesized from one or several original features and represents a

generalized assessment of objects with respect to class separation [6, 7].

The following tasks must be solved:

1. Determine optimal class-separating intervals for quantitative features.
2. Replace nominal feature gradations by membership-function values.
3. Transform heterogeneous features into a unified binary representation.
4. Compute feature stability and informativeness measures.
5. Apply agglomerative hierarchical grouping to synthesize latent features.
6. Construct a reduced latent feature space based on generalized assessments.
7. Evaluate the effectiveness of the new feature space using classification algorithms.

These tasks follow the general idea of transforming heterogeneous features and synthesizing latent features by hierarchical agglomerative grouping [6, 7, 10].

The values of a quantitative feature $x_c, c \in I$ for objects in E_0 are arranged in non-decreasing order:

$$r_1, \dots, r_j, \dots, r_h, \text{ where } h = |K_1 \cup K_2| \quad (1)$$

Let $d_{tc}(u, v)$ and $d_{3-t,c}(u, v)$ denote the number of objects from classes K_t, K_{3-t} falling into the interval $[r_u; r_v]^i, i \in \{1, \dots, p_c\}$. The boundaries of the intervals are determined by recursive optimization of the following criterion:

$$\left| \frac{d_{tc}(u, v)}{|K_t|} - \frac{d_{3-t,c}(u, v)}{|K_{3-t}|} \right| \rightarrow \max \quad (2)$$

The nonlinear transformation replaces the original feature values with the values of the membership function to the classes [7, 10]. For a quantitative feature $x_c \in X(n)$, the membership function $f_c(\mu)$ for class K_1 in each interval $[r_u; r_v]^\mu$ is calculated as:

$$f_c(\mu) = \frac{d_{tc}(u, v) / K_{tc}}{d_{tc}(u, v) / K_{tc} + d_{3-tc}(u, v) / K_{3-tc}} \quad (3)$$

$$G_c = \frac{q1+q2}{2} \quad (4)$$

For nominal features, gradations are directly replaced by membership function values [6, 7, 10]. The

boundary between classes G_c is determined by formula (4). The contribution of each feature to the generalized assessment and the stability $\Psi(c)$ are then computed.

Proposed methodology for nonlinear transformation and latent feature synthesis.

1. General scheme of the proposed method.

The proposed methodology consists of four main stages and follows the general scheme of nonlinear transformation, generalized assessment calculation, and latent feature synthesis [6, 7, 10]. At the first stage, the original heterogeneous feature space is analyzed according to the type of each feature. At the second stage, quantitative and nominal features are transformed using class-membership information. At the third stage, feature weights, stability, and generalized assessments are computed. At the fourth stage, agglomerative hierarchical grouping is applied to synthesize a compact set of latent features [6, 7].

The general structure of the method can be written as follows:

$$X^{(n)} \rightarrow X_b \rightarrow Y^{(k)} \rightarrow \text{Classifier},$$

where $X^{(n)}$ is the original heterogeneous feature space, X_b is the transformed binary feature space, $Y^{(k)}$ is the synthesized latent feature space, and the final classifier may be NN, KNN, SVM, or another recognition algorithm [6, 11, 12].

2. Preprocessing and transformation to binary space. The set of objects is divided into two classes (K_1 and K_2). For each feature:

- *Quantitative features* — values are sorted, and optimal intervals are found using recursive optimization.
- *Nominal features* — gradations are replaced by membership function values.

As a result, all features are unified into a *binary space* {1,2} [7, 10].

3. Stability and generalized assessments. The stability $\Psi(c)$ of each feature is calculated. The generalized assessment $R(S_r)$ is computed for every object and treated as a new latent feature [6, 7].

4. Agglomerative hierarchical grouping. In the binary space, feature weights are calculated as $w_c = \beta_c \times \lambda_c$, where β_c is intra-class similarity and λ_c is inter-class difference. Using a greedy algorithm, features

with high stability are selected as initiators to form groups. This process produces a significantly smaller latent feature space Y [6, 7].

Computational experiments.

The computational experiments were conducted on three different types of datasets: quantitative, nominal, and mixed [13-15]. This makes it possible to evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed dimensionality reduction method for heterogeneous data measured in different scales.

In each experiment, the original feature space was transformed into a reduced latent feature space, and the classification accuracy was compared before and after transformation. The results show that the synthesized latent features improve the performance of NN, KNN, and SVM classifiers.

1. Quantitative features. The first experiment was conducted on the *Hypertension dataset*, which represents the group of quantitative features [13]. The original dataset contained 29 features and 147 objects.

After applying the proposed dimensionality reduction method, the original feature space was reduced to 8 latent features. This reduced feature space was then used to evaluate the recognition accuracy of the NN and KNN algorithms.

Table 1. Recognition accuracy on the Hypertension dataset

Algorithm	Accuracy in original feature space (%)	Accuracy in latent feature space (%)
NN	55.6	89.0
KNN	65.0	91.0

The results show that transforming the original quantitative feature space into a reduced latent feature space significantly improves the recognition accuracy of both NN and KNN algorithms.

In particular, the KNN algorithm achieved the highest accuracy, increasing from 65.0% in the original feature space to 91.0% in the latent feature space.

2. Nominal features. The second experiment was conducted on the *Uzbek-Korean psychological dataset*, which represents the group of nominal features [14]. The original

dataset contained 24 features and 100 objects.

After applying the proposed dimensionality reduction method, the original feature space was reduced to 2 latent features.

Table 2. Recognition accuracy on the Uzbek-Korean psychological dataset

Algorithm	Accuracy in original feature space (%)	Accuracy in latent feature space (%)
NN	71.0	91.08
KNN	61.0	93.6

In particular, the KNN algorithm achieved the highest accuracy, increasing from **61.0%** in the original feature space to **93.6%** in the latent feature space.

3. Mixed-type features. The third experiment was conducted on the *Heart-Disease dataset*, which represents the group of **mixed features** [15]. The original dataset contained **13 features**, including **7 nominal features** and **6 quantitative features**, and **270 objects**.

After applying the proposed dimensionality reduction method, the original feature space was reduced to **2 latent features**. This reduced feature space was then used to evaluate the recognition accuracy of the NN, KNN, and SVM algorithms [11, 12].

Table 3. Recognition accuracy on the Heart-Disease dataset

Algorithm	Accuracy in original feature space (%)	Accuracy in latent feature space (%)
NN	41.0	85.0
KNN	56.0	82.0
SVM, RBF kernel	33.3	88.8

The results show that the proposed transformation is also effective for mixed datasets containing both nominal and quantitative features.

Among the tested algorithms, **SVM with RBF kernel** achieved the highest recognition accuracy in the latent feature space, increasing from **33.3%** to **88.8%** [11, 12].

Figures 1 and 2 illustrate the distribution of objects from the Heart-Disease dataset in the original and latent feature spaces, respectively. In Figure 1, the

objects of the two classes are considerably overlapped, indicating weak separability in the original feature representation. In contrast, Figure 2 demonstrates a clearer separation of the classes after the construction of latent features. This confirms that the proposed transformation improves the discriminative structure of the data, which is also reflected in the higher recognition accuracy achieved by the SVM classifier with the RBF kernel.

Figure 1. Visualization of objects in the original feature space.

Figure 2. Visualization of objects in the latent feature space.

Analysis of results. The proposed method allows reducing the dimensionality of the feature space by around 2 to 15 times while significantly improving classifier accuracy, which is consistent with the general role of dimensionality reduction and feature transformation in improving learning performance [1, 3, 5, 8]. The main advantages of the method are:

- Unification of heterogeneous (quantitative and nominal) features into a single binary space;
- Good interpretability of results due to the use of generalized assessments;
- Flexibility for big data problems.

Conclusion. In this work, an effective methodology has been developed for transforming the

raw feature space into a binary space followed by the synthesis of latent features using agglomerative hierarchical grouping [6, 7, 10]. The conducted experiments confirm the high efficiency of the proposed approach. In the future, it is planned to extend the method to multi-class problems and combine it with deep neural networks.

References

1. Guyon I., Elisseeff A. An Introduction to Variable and Feature Selection // *Journal of Machine Learning Research*. 2003. Vol. 3. P. 1157–1182.
2. Тухтабаев К.А., Эргашева Ш.Э. Аналитические выражения для вычисления значений латентных признаков // *Proceedings of the Seminar dedicated to the memory of professor M.I. Isroilov, CMT2024*. Tashkent, 2024. P. 159–162.
3. Jolliffe I.T. *Principal Component Analysis*. 2nd ed. New York: Springer, 2002.
4. van der Maaten L., Hinton G. Visualizing Data using t-SNE // *Journal of Machine Learning Research*. 2008. Vol. 9. P. 2579–2605.
5. Tenenbaum J.B., de Silva V., Langford J.C. A Global Geometric Framework for Nonlinear Dimensionality Reduction // *Science*. 2000. Vol. 290. No. 5500. P. 2319–2323.
6. Ignatev N.A., Akbarov B.K., Tuhtabayev K.A. Deriving Analytical Expressions for Calculating the Values of Latent Features in Recognition Problems // *Problems of Computational and Applied Mathematics*. 2023. No. 6/1(54). P. 68–76.
7. Ergasheva Sh.E. Dimensionality Reduction of Feature Space Using Nonlinear Transformations of Heterogeneous Features // *Education, Science and Innovative Ideas in the World*. 2024.
8. Belkin M., Niyogi P. Laplacian Eigenmaps for Dimensionality Reduction and Data Representation // *Neural Computation*. 2003. Vol. 15. No. 6. P. 1373–1396.
9. Garouani, M., Barhrhouj, A. & Teste, O. (2025) XStacking: An Effective and Inherently Explainable Framework for Stacked Ensemble

Learning. *Information Fusion*. vol. 124. Article 103358. doi: 10.1016/j.inffus.2025.103358.

10. Ignatev N.A. On Nonlinear Transformations of Features Based on the Functions of Objects Belonging to Classes // *Pattern Recognition and Image Analysis*. 2021. Vol. 31. No. 2. P. 197–204.
11. Bishop C.M. *Pattern Recognition and Machine Learning*. New York: Springer, 2006.
12. Hastie T., Tibshirani R., Friedman J. *The Elements of Statistical Learning: Data Mining, Inference, and Prediction*. 2nd ed. New York: Springer, 2009.
13. Hypertension dataset. Internal experimental medical dataset for hypertension analysis, consisting of 147 objects and 29 quantitative features. [Online] Available from: <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1I022n-Jw9jUwejZ556K65LJNh77pf4hx> (Accessed: 11 May 2026).
14. Uzbek-Korean dataset. Internal experimental psychological dataset consisting of 100 objects and 24 nominal features. [Online] Available from: <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1wdavuSmbvWLojNX51mruu0XzgImr0Hg2> (Accessed: 11 May 2026).
15. UCI Repository of Machine Learning Databases. Heart-Disease. [Online] Available from: <http://archive.ics.uci.edu/ml/datasets/Heart+Disease> (Accessed: 11 May 2026).

